

Chapters

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I am sharing my thoughts on the fundamental fabric of the universe, every new unread concept I write in this book is merely my own words and imagination, not beyond or proved. I hope it will be close to the theory of everything.

In the summer of 2024, spending time alone in turin italy, made me think about the universe, and this is the result of it.

1. Introduction

The theory of interaction is a geometrical system that creates a visualisation of the system of fabric.

I might change, remove or add to the details or the important parts of this book later but I believe in the main concept of interaction for the fabric. Every phenomenon has to be happening by the direct interaction of little individual cells that particles and the space between the particles are made of. I imagine this is how things move or turns into energy or anything else. Everything, whether space of particles, are only different states of these fabric cells. And in this theory, different state of being means having more rotational speed and the shape of fabric cell, is like a string that by rotation shapes a bubble. And they are in a direct touch with each other, interacting and sharing rotational speed.

everything is made of them but with an important difference compared to the traditional views. A mass does not own specific particles, mass is only a trapped wave among fabric cells, like a maelstrom among water molecules that can travel among water molecules and each moment its having different water molecules shaping it. It is just an energy, concentrated in a point that tends to stay there not to move anymore due to the specific shape and limitations of the fabric cells, and that's why I focus on describing my imagination about the geometrical system of the fabric.

While in this book I'm sharing only one possible imagination about the reality due to not having enough clues to reduce the possibility of other systems to zero, I can't guarantee this, especially that I'm not using a mathematical framework to prove it, maybe one day I will. But this theory looks completely wise and fine for me to describe the reality and fill the gap

between general relativity and quantum mechanics. However it is not made of these two in fact it shares an individual concept and description about the universe. Because maybe quantum mechanics or general relativity have problems and flaws that they can't match the reality.

Mass is only a concentrated amount of energy trapped in a triangular shape of fabric particles, where energy is only a higher oscillation level among fabric particles. Theory of interaction means we live in an ocean of particles, the particles are all interacting with adjacent particles touching and transferring their oscillation to each other. The geometrical shape of particles and their system have a limitation for oscillation rate, and at a certain rate of oscillation they get trapped in a triangular shape making three particles as the core, and continue oscillating inside that triangle of three particles, and if released, a large amount of energy is produced, again, energy is only oscillation among fabric particles.

In this view the direct visualisation and concept of the relation of energy-mass conversion is well-demonstrated, where I describe mass as the densest form of energy trapped in a point due to the geometrical shape of fabric particles. I want to make you imagine this geometrical system which I suggest, to have a more understandable view about reality, however quite different.

Particles exist between masses, and the direct interaction of particles between objects is how gravity or light and energy are transferred, it's more of a connection.

Energy, light and gravity are only different oscillation rates among particles being transferred to the next particles due to the difference of oscillation rate and the geometrical structure of the system of fabric particles.

Bigger particles are all different states of fabric particles in action, like electrons which are not individual particles, electrons are only a wave of response, made by the dynamic change of three sides of the core triangle, each moment inside of atoms.

An important point, when a mass moves, it is having new particles inside of it by any moment. When you move your hand to the right, fabric particles that were shaping your hand in the previous moment, are now shaping air molecules. You might imagine impossible due to the different density of atoms in the comparison of our hand and air, but the more mass and density of our hand means more trapped energy, which is able to be transferred among particles, so the difference between denser and less denser areas is the difference between inside of a maelstrom with calm water. This is how weight is defined.

1. Interaction: the geometrical system

This theory is suggesting a different system for the whole physical phenomenon happening in our reality.

But firstly I should mention that it might sound weird and different at the base level but the system quite reasons all phenomena.

The theory of interaction suggests that we live in an ocean of little tiny particles, the fabric of the universe, imagined as strings or bubbles interacting directly with each other touching and handling each other and every possible phenomenon is due to the interaction of fabric cells or let's say particles of the universe with each other.

In this view this interaction is considered as a transfer of rotational movement where each particle is rotating or oscillating around its own axis, and every particle is directly rotating the other particles around, all causing the rotation of each other and each individual particle playing its part in this ocean of rotating particles, but surely they are not rotating in a messy way, because otherwise they would have stopped each other. However in the simple basic view in the theory they are not being moved to anywhere when a mass moves. Mass is just a high rotational speed of particles being transferred among them, which I'm willing to describe in this book in more detail.

In this suggested system particles are rotating other particles in two directions, horizontal and vertical. You might ask compared to what, let's slowly get to the point.

Imagine these little particles, coordinate in a very big circular circumference, like a polygon with a very big number of sides and all particles rotate each other in the horizontal direction along to each one of them. So they must have the same speed as the average speed of particles in this circumference, because each one of them is entangled with adjacent particles around.

Now imagine a slightly smaller circular circumference inside the first circumference, and in both circumferences, each particle adjacent to another particle of the other circumference is rotating the other particle in the vertical direction of itself. And this smaller circumference surely has a smaller number of fabric particles, and because of the direct touch of entangled particles, each circumference has to have the same overall speed of rotation of particles that of the other circumference in a back and forth way. It means the average speed of particles increases by going to a smaller circumference because the smaller circumference has less number of particles but the same overall rotational speed, because of being responsible to rotate the particles of the other circumference which consists of more particles.

Now imagine a third smaller circumference inner side entangled with the inner side of second smallest circumference, having the same overall speed of the first big circumference, but surely more average speed because of the less number of particles, more than the second smallest. As you go smaller and smaller the shape of the fabric particles gradually change because of having more rotational speed, they turn their circular shape into an elliptical shape,

as you go smaller and smaller you reach circular circumferences with very less number of particles with the same overall speed meaning with really faster speed of individual particles compared to bigger circumferences, reaching polygons, going smaller having smaller polygons and at the end, the smallest polygon with the most elliptical form of particles that each one is close to shape a line due to having the high rotational speed around their own axis, a triangle, with three particles, three sides, related to three quarks system. However it can be for sure controversial because of seeing a difference between the planck length is 10^{-35} but the size of a quark is measured to be 10^{-20} . In this case we can bring up some imaginations like what planck measured is maybe something about the length of strings or the change of the size of strings or let's say particles by transferring a difference of the rotational speed among each other. Or we can say the planck length is the diameter of strings but quarks are made of a structure of many strings. Out of this theory of interaction

we can imagine quarks as a sort of different shapes of strings but it doesn't fit the fact that energy can produce mass and mass can produce pure energy, the fact that mass and energy are exactly the same thing.

In this view mass is just a concentrated form of energy trapped in a triangular shape that due to the geometrical limitations we can't have more rotational speed in our dimension.

Every phenomenon happen through this interaction. Gravity, light and

2. gravity

In the simple word, when the particles around a core gets rotated faster, the core will now appear among those particles, so the core is transferred to adjacent particles.

Another mass can do this increase of rotation, so the two cores of rotation can help each other to happen closer and closer, so it's a double effect of increase of distance.

imagine two masses, two mass as described by the theory, rotate the particles around them. So when mass number 1 rotates the particles around mass number 2, it increases the rotational speed among particles for both masses, so the closest particles to each core of rotation will get rotated as fast as the core, and the core will have a lower rotational speed and adjacent particles will now be the core. In this way two masses attract each other, But in fact there is no concept like two separated masses, masses are only trapped maximum central rotational speed among particles or MCRS, and collection of MCRSs effect each other to happen closer to each other. This would have to describe how the macroscopic rotation of two objects avoid their approach towards each other.

By visualising how interaction of fabric particles work, it is not difficult to imagine how two trapped core of oscillation among fabric particles can cause the attraction of cores(masses). As the two cores are the response to the increase of rotational speed among fabric particles, the particles around the core are being rotated as well in the coordinated direction respected to each core.

It is essential to understand the system of interaction. A very large amount of rotational speed is among fabric particles of the universe, but due to the limitations of the geometrical shape of fabric cell, it is not possible to have all this rotational speed on a few particles, because fabric particles cannot have more than a specific speed, as of the shape of the particles are specified. That's why light is the limitation speed.

Fabric particles get in an elliptical shape as they get rotated more and more and at a certain shape they coordinate in a dynamic triangle of particles, which is changing its sides simultaneously.

It is not possible to have the maximum central rotational speed(MCRS) in more rotational speed, because of their geometrical shape limitation, they transfer the rotation to other particles.

3. Light

As of describing the theory of interaction and the geometrical system of fabric movement, let me describe what light is according to this theory.

Simply light is a difference of rotational speed among particles in a circumference. it is immediately transferred to the next particle of the next circumference and is seen as a wave. difference in the rotational speed of a single particle compared to other particles of that circumference, will immediately cause the drs(difference of the rotational speed) to move to the next circumference, because the particles of each circumference are fixed in a chain alignment as one single unit of rotation.

When in a circumference of particles, one particle finds a higher rotational speed, it immediately transfers this rotational speed to the next particle of the next circumference, because they are in a direct touch, or in interaction. so this wave of interaction continues and might be affected by other cores(MCRSs) that could attract the transfer to closer particles to themselves.

We can only detect something if it shares waves like light, in fact when a fabric cell has a difference of oscillation rate among all cells, it transfers this higher oscillation to next cells, and what we detect is this difference of oscillation or let's say difference of rotational speed. We only can detect this difference of oscillation, not the fixed rotational speed of fabric cells or the cells themself.

4. Energy and vibration

To describe the vibration of atoms according to the theory of interaction, it's better to describe the structure and system of the core. It is all about the dynamic change of the triangle, which is transferred to the adjacent cells that are closest to the maximum rotational speed. The fabric cells of the core triangle that are rotated by the maximum speed are in the

most elliptical shape close to the shape of a flat plate, in this shape it can't rotate faster because of this geometrical shape limitation. But let's describe how it goes.

When the three fabric cells of the core are rotating, a cycle is repeated by every moment. In this cycle, one of the cells stay and the other two starts moving their joining points to the stationary cell by the length of the cell to the center of it, when the two cells meet their joining points in the center of the stationary side(cell), the stationary cell now rotates as fast as possible, then the other two cells get their other edges on another cell, and the previous third cell shares its rotational speed with all the adjacent cells, as the rotational speed gets in balance again, new third cell is a part of the triangle now, and now one of these three sides of the triangle acts as the third part, and this is how the triangle transfers among cells.

Energy is higher average rotational speed for the cells so it causes the cores to vibrate faster.

5. Electron

This theory changes the definition of particles as defined in modern physics.

Dark matter, electrons, protons and all other particles are only different states of the same unit.

Electron is only a wave of response to the dynamic change of the core triangle.

When the core triangle changes one side the third side releases the rotation among adjacent cells and due to the fixed structure of rotational speed for all the cells, the released rotational speed goes as a wave among cells and gets further, but immediately come back because the new third cell eats this rotational speed, to become faster to get the triangle complete in balance again.

I might be completely wrong in the details of the geometrical shape and description of it, but what I think is true, is that the electrons are only a back and forth reaction among cells to the dynamic change inside of the core.

6. Black holes

According to the theory of interaction the structure of Black hole is a multiplied of many triangles entangled to each other, it is exactly a massive core like the core of a heavy atom.

The structure of a heavy atom core is a combination of triangles sharing sides with each other. In this structure the corner triangles are protons and the center triangles are not able to make a back and forth response with adjacent cells outside of the core, so they won't cause electrons happening among the cells outside of the core. So we call these non electron maker triangles, neutrons.

A black hole is a massive simulation of heavy atom cores.

At a specific number for the ratio of inner triangles to outer triangles, the electrons can't happen by the outer triangles, when the structure and balance of the need for shaping inner triangles equals with the need to shaping outer triangles, and every higher rotational speed that comes to this structure, only helps to add to the number of triangles, and this is how a black hole eats everything around or rotates everything around.

7. Time

Well there is nothing like time as we imagine. It is all about changes, not time. We consider one movement of small hand of clock calling it one second as a change that we compare other changes rates and durations with. But time is not something that controls everything. It's just something we measure rates with, but reality is about direct forces and mass, and nothing is controlling the reality from outside or something universal from the inner side that we can reach and change the combination of all forces and mass with it. If you wanna reach the combination of your body as it was 20 years ago, you can't press any button to get to that form again like that, you gotta directly deal with the position of each single atom inside you to coordinate them as it was 20 years ago. Reality is what you have now, and by the time passing it just changes its combination, a bit of energy to mass a bit of mass to energy, the combination of atoms together, the atoms we have now were made billions of years ago, we just have them now in another structure and combination with each other, like the atoms of your coffee were under soil maybe less than a year ago in another form. It's just the energy dealing with atoms, and actually in my theory atoms are concentrated energy points, or let's clarify it according to the theory, energy is just that rotation of the particles that vary,

so all we are in and made of, is fabric particles being vibrated or rotated and transferring this rotation among each other. It can describe mass, energy, force and light as the same thing in different processes. We usually talk about time in a way we imagine it as a button that we can press and then switch the reality into the form it was in the past or it will be in the future, but time is just a measurement scale that we humans put on the changes rates to understand and compare the changes. But it's all about changes not time, you put your meat outside, if the weather is warm it will be rotten in a day or two. But if you put it in a freezer it will last longer. You didn't shorten the time for the meat, you just tried to slow the change rate by decreasing the temperature.